

A Comparative Analysis of AI Models for Transit Time Prediction in Transportation Systems

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Abstract. The Time-critical term emphasizes the dominance of time as a factor in systems, operations, processes, and activities. As an example, processing animal by-products is a time-critical process as the material can rapidly degrade and become potentially harmful; hence, not suitable to be used as raw material in added value products. In this industry, time estimation increases flexibility in decision-making in logistics and processes. This paper presents a comparative review of AI algorithms that predict the transit time of by-product containers from slaughterhouses to the processing facilities. The prediction allows the logistic planner to schedule the logistic resources earlier than usual. Consequently, the generated delay in the logistics can be reduced, or even eliminated. The trained models used real collected data from a processing facility for 10 months. Among several AI algorithms, both Decision Tree and Extra Trees regressors provided the lowest error. Then, the Voting Ensemble of these two models provided better results and higher stability.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Transit Time Prediction, Data Analytics, Feature Engineering.

1 Introduction

Organic by-products from animal food production are usually not fit for human consumption. Nonetheless, they are used as raw materials to produce a wide range of commodities such as animal food, fertilizers, and biofuels, which in return, increases the sustainability of the entire food chain and improves the environmental impact [1].

According to EU legislation EU 1069/2009 [2] and EU 142/2011 [3], the quality and category of the animal by-products depend on two main factors: the contents of the by-products and the age of the by-product. These two factors affect the types and quality of the produced commodities [4]. Therefore, it is necessary to optimize the logistics activities to maximize the quality of the by-products. One of the main challenges in this optimization problem is the narrow time window for the material before it starts

decomposing. This time-critical nature increases the constraints and reduces the margin around the optimal solution.

With a substantial need to find solutions to improve the environmental impact, the EU Commission is funding several research projects. One of these projects is titled Optimizing Production and Logistic Resources in the Time-critical Bio Production Industries in Europe (CLARUS) [5]. CLARUS project, funded by the EU Commission, intends to develop AI solutions for improving and sustaining the food industry. To validate the project goals, Honkajoki Oy – the leading animal by-product processing company in Finland- has been chosen in a use case involving logistics optimization. One scenario of this use case involves optimizing the selection of time-critical containers with the highest quality, i.e., category three material [3], of animal by-products for transportation from slaughterhouses to Honkajoki’s processing facilities. In this regard, this paper presents the performance results of several machine-learning models trained on historical logistics data. The main objective of this research is to provide an empirical comparison of AI algorithms that provide accurate predictions of the transit duration of the material. Such a prediction may help the end users to react early, enlarging the narrow time window.

This paper is structured into several sections. The introduction section provides the context of the paper and the CLARUS project. Section 2 contains insights into by-product logistics optimization and the goal of forecasting the transit time. The approach developed to tackle the issue is explained in Section 3, while the preliminary results are presented in Section 4. Lastly, Section 5 describes the concluding remarks and potential next research steps.

2 Review of animal by-product logistics

Logistics is an integral part of supply chains and directly influences expenses [6]. Not only does optimized logistics improve supply chains’ efficiency and enhance customer satisfaction, but it also leads companies toward greenness and sustainability. Better logistics means better resource allocation, less energy consumption, and less pollution [7]. Moreover, due to their deteriorating nature, food products differ from other types of material; hence, they require specific needs in their transportation [8].

In the case of Honkajoki Oy, logistics is of great significance since the material that is processed is highly time-critical. Raw material degrades gradually; thus, it should arrive at the factory for processing as soon as possible. Otherwise, the material quality would decrease to lower categories that require much more energy to process or be discarded due to the biochemical and chemical deterioration of the contents, especially in the case of category three animal by-products [3]. In the use case mentioned in this paper, category three chicken by-products are transported from three slaughterhouses to the Honkajoki processing facility by fleets of trucks. In a scenario, there can be multiple filled containers waiting for transport. To this end, an optimization algorithm is designed to analyze and guide operators in selecting suitable containers waiting at the slaughterhouse yards for transport in order to maximize the quality and the number of category three containers. This optimization algorithm uses a machine learning model

that predicts the container transit time from slaughterhouses to the Honkajoki factory yard instead of using average values. This paper is solely presenting the work carried out in the design and development of the transit time prediction model.

3 Approach

3.1 Data Collection

In the Honkajoki use case, the data collection and management system is arranged according to the system map shown in **Fig. 1**. Honkajoki has collected several years' worth of logistics and processing data and stored them on an Amazon AWS server (called Honkajoki Cloud). Historical logistics data used in the scenario described in this paper are collected from the Honkajoki Electronic Logistic System (HELOS) hosted within the Honkajoki cloud. The logistics data include container and truck data and timestamps of all logistics actions. This logistics data includes *containerID* for container identification, *slaughterhouse* for marking the source of the material, *category* that describes the material type, and *plate* to identify the transporting truck. In addition, the data includes time stamps for *filling_started*, *filling_ended*, *container_pickedup*, and *container_arrived*.

Fig. 1. Honkajoki system map

3.2 Data Modelling

The dataset used in this research holds information on containers, such as their raw material type, weight, and the slaughterhouse they have filled. Also, there are logistics-related attributes, e.g., the truck plate, the timestamp when a container finishes filling, and the timestamp when a truck reaches the Honkajoki yard.

Intuitively, the transit time of containers from slaughterhouses to the yard should depend on the time trucks leave slaughterhouses, which slaughterhouse they depart from, and the plate numbers identifying trucks. Since weighing containers takes place only after reaching the Honkajoki yard, the weight of containers is not available in HELOS, and we have not considered it. Consequently, the corresponding features were selected in the preprocessing stage, and the string attributes, i.e., slaughterhouse name and plate number, were encoded to numerical values. Afterward, the timestamps were divided into four subparts, namely week number, weekday number, hour, and minute. **Fig. 2** shows five random rows of the dataset for training transit time predictors.

	SH	Plate	Leaving Week No.	Leaving Day	Leaving Hour	Leaving Minute
0	0	0	24	4	1	17
1	0	2	18	1	12	40
2	1	5	22	3	7	57
3	1	8	52	1	20	54
4	0	2	1	3	1	18

Fig. 2. A brief overview of the dataset after preprocessing

The time difference in seconds between trucks leaving the slaughterhouse and arrival at the yard was used as labels to train the models. A sample of the transit time of containers from slaughterhouse 1 (SH1) recorded in the historical dataset from 5/12/2022 to 25/12/2022 and their departure timestamps are plotted in **Fig. 3**.

Fig. 3. Container transit time plot

3.3 Prediction Model Development

Predictive analytics uses historical data and statistics to analyze trends and predict or forecast the data. Predictive analytics is done by utilizing statistical algorithms and machine learning algorithms, allowing organizations to be proactive in situations in the future based on examining predicted data. Hence, predictive analytics has grown significantly, and multiple machine learning algorithms for various prediction tasks, including time-series forecasting, have been developed to improve the overall accuracy of the forecasted data [9] [10] [11].

As seen in Section 3.2, the training dataset is irregularly sampled and multi-variate, which impacts the choice of algorithms for designing transit time prediction models. Thus, the transit time prediction problem is currently solved by using regressors instead of time-series prediction and analysis tools due to the robustness of regression algorithms in handling such data.

Commonly used regression algorithms in time-series forecasting and predictive analysis, such as deep learning regressors, e.g., multi-layer perceptron (MLP) and long short-term memory (LSTM) neural networks, and ensemble learning algorithms, such as Random Forest regressor were considered for this use case. The models considered for testing are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Machine learning algorithms used for testing.

Machine learning technique	Algorithm
Ensemble Learning	Random Forest regressor
	Decision Tree regressor
	Gradient Boosting regressor
	Extreme Gradient Boosting regressor
	Extra Trees regressor
	Voting regressor
Deep Learning	LSTM neural network regressor
	MLP neural network regressor

4 Preliminary results

In this paper, ensemble learning models are created using existing algorithms from the Scikit-learn Python library [12], except for the Extreme Gradient Boosting regressor that is a part of the XGBoost library. On the other hand, deep learning models use components from the TensorFlow library. Several models from the algorithms are created with multiple parameter configurations, e.g., different numbers of layers and neurons in the case of neural networks. The configurations yielding the best results based on mean absolute error (MAE) are shown in Table 2. Additionally, a linear regression model was used as the baseline for comparison.

The logistics data is randomly split into training and test sets with a ratio of 4:1, and all the models are trained and tested with the same dataset. The performance results of all the models are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Model performance comparison.

Algorithm/Models	Additional configuration	MAE (seconds)
Random Forest regressor	No maximum tree depth	491
Decision Tree regressor	-	381
Gradient Boosting regressor	-	753
Support Vector Machine regressor	-	832
Extreme Gradient Boosting regressor	-	464
Extra Trees regressor	-	285
Voting regressor	Combination of Extra Trees regressor & Decision Tree regressor	357
LSTM neural network model 1	2 layers, 64 units each (51265 parameters)	900
LSTM neural network model 2	2 layers, 128 units each (200833 parameters)	895
LSTM neural network model 3	3 layers, 64 units each (84289 parameters)	964
MLP neural network model 1	2 layers, 128 units each (17550 parameters)	985
MLP neural network model 2	2 layers, 256 units each (67854 parameters)	925
MLP neural network model 3	3 layers, 128 units each (34062 parameters)	895
Linear regression (baseline)	N/A	951

Table 2 shows that ensemble learning models perform better than deep learning models and the baseline model using the current dataset and input modeling method in terms of prediction accuracy with lower MAE margin. The voting regressor combines Decision Tree and Extra Trees regressors, which already have low error margins, to produce final predictions with the lowest MAE. According to Table 2, the extra trees regressor performs the best; however, since there is randomness involved with this method, the voting regressor combining the two best-performing models was chosen to ensure the stability of the predictions. Additionally, from testing results, while increasing the number of trainable parameters to the deep learning models can improve the forecasting results in some cases, the improvements do not scale well with the training cost of the models.

5 Conclusion

Processing animal by-products is a time-critical operation that requires minimizing any wasted time. The process itself can be well-planned. However, the transportation of the material from the slaughterhouses to the processing facility may cause delays and unplanned changes. Thus, predicting such disruptions in the logistic operations improves the overall result of the process of the by-product. As presented in this paper, AI-trained model on historical data can provide the needed prediction. As observed in this research, regression algorithms trained with multi-variate and irregularly sampled can perform prediction tasks low error measures. Additionally, among the examined regression algorithms, Voting Regressor combining Decision Tree and Extra Trees regressors provides the lowest error and better stability. Future work may include further testing results from other prediction algorithms and approaches to feature engineering. According to the requirements of the original scenario of the use case, the results from the optimization algorithm using data produced by prediction models will also be presented in the future.

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